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“ARENDELLE RAE, MY LIGHTHOUSE”

Dear Arendelle Rae, my bright spot,
A love so vast, a name well sought.
Like the sunrise that renews the sky,
You shine with grace as time drifts by.

Your laughter rings, so light, so free,
Like rippling waves upon the sea.
Each step you take, a song so sweet,
A melody that feels complete.

With eyes that hold the morning's gleam,
You chase the world, you chase your dream.
Your heart is kind, your spirit bold,
A story yet to be retold.

You bloom with grace, so pure, so true,
Like flowers kissed by drops of dew.
No storm nor wind can dim your fire,
Your strength will lift you ever higher.

Oh, Arendelle Rae, my child so dear,
You fill my days with joy sincere.
Your tiny hands, once soft and small,
Now reaching high, so strong, so tall.

May kindness be your guiding way,
A light for those who've lost the day.
May wisdom shape the path you tread,
And courage walk where dreams are led.

Through trials fierce and moments grim,
Let love and faith not fade nor dim.
For in your soul, a spark divine,
A light that always dares to shine.

Arendelle Rae, my heart's embrace,
In you, I see the world's own grace.
No matter where the road may bend,
My love will guide you to the end.

So go, my child, with hopeful gaze,
Embrace the world, set hearts ablaze.
For you are meant to soar with grace,
Arendelle Rae, in Mama's embrace.

